

Project acronym: EOSC4CANCER
Grant Agreement Number: 101058427
Project full title: A European-wide foundation to
accelerate Data-driven Cancer Research
Call identifier: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01

D5.3 First content of the RDMkit Cancer View

Version: 1.0
Status: Final
Dissemination Level: Public
Deliverable Type: Report
Due date of deliverable: 30.06.2024
Actual submission date: 27.06.2025
Work Package: WP 5 Training and capacity building for key national and international stakeholders
Lead partner for this deliverable: CNIO
Partner(s) contributing: CERTH, HEALTH RI, EATRIS, UNIMAN, BBMRI

Main author(s):

Fotis Psomopoulos	INAB CERTH
Fatima Al-Shahrour	CNIO

Other author(s):

Sarah Morgan	EATRIS	Celia van Gelder	Health-RI/DTL
Munazah Andrabi	UNIMAN	Kurt Majcen	BBMRI
Fieke Schoots	Health-RI/DTL		

Abstract

The EOSC4Cancer initiative addresses the pressing need for advanced research and infrastructure in tackling cancer, particularly in Europe. This document focuses on the WP5 initiative within EOSC4Cancer, which aims to empower clinicians and cancer researchers through capacity building by designing a coherent training portfolio related to cancer data research following the national needs, and complementary to national efforts. This document outlines the initial design process of a dedicated RDMkit Cancer View will be utilized to effectively offer this portfolio for use by trainers as well as for self training purposes.

Revision History

Version	Date	Changes made	Author(s)
0.1	25.06.2024	Initial draft	Fotis Psomopoulos (INAB CERTH), Fátima Al-Shahrour (CNIO) Serena Scollen (ELIXIR Hub)
0.4	24.06.2024	Review of the D5.3 page	Daniel Barrowdale (ELIXIR Hub) Flora D'Anna (VIB / ELIXIR Belgium)
1.0	27.06.2024	Final review of the report	Fotis Psomopoulos (INAB CERTH), Fátima Al-Shahrour (CNIO)

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1 Introduction	5
2 RDMKit	6
3 RDMKit Cancer View	7

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Introduction

Cancer, a complex and pervasive disease affecting individuals worldwide, demands a concerted effort for prevention, diagnosis, and treatment. With Europe shouldering a disproportionate cancer burden, the need for advanced research and infrastructure is paramount. The EOSC4Cancer initiative seeks to leverage existing resources and community solutions, establishing a federated FAIR data, analysis, and services infrastructure dedicated to European Cancer research programs. In the face of escalating data complexity and technological advancements, effective analysis and interpretation of cancer research data have emerged as critical components for understanding the disease and enhancing treatment outcomes. The WP5 initiative within EOSC4Cancer is committed to empowering clinicians and cancer researchers with the requisite skills and knowledge to leverage the project's tools and infrastructure effectively, both during and beyond the project lifecycle. A key element in this effort is the development of the RDMkit Cancer View page, that aims to provide direct guidance around cancer research data management.

RDMkit Cancer View

The ELIXIR Research Data Management Kit (RDMkit) is a comprehensive resource designed to help life scientists manage their research data in accordance with the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) Principles. Developed by the ELIXIR community, with the support of the EU-funded ELIXIR-CONVERGE project (grant agreement 871075), the RDMkit offers guidance and best practices covering all stages of the data lifecycle, from planning and acquisition to analysis and dissemination. It also provides information on software tools, standards, and repositories relevant to research data management.

In this report we describe the design process of the RDMKit Cancer View page that focuses on the specific challenges of managing cancer data, structured around the patient journey (prevention, diagnosis, and treatment). The RDMKit Cancer View page aims to facilitate better cancer data management practices, supporting clinical decision-making and cancer research through well-organized, FAIR-compliant data management strategies. The RDMKit Cancer View page will continuously integrate feedback from EOSC4Cancer members and other stakeholders and currently consists of six sections representing the different stages of the patient journey and their respective challenges in data management.

The RDMKit Cancer View document is still in its initial phase and future work is also described, including; ensuring domain-specific content from data management perspective, incorporating diverse cancer-related data, documenting best practices (RDLC, B1MG) and providing context for standards and resources.

1 Introduction

Cancer is a heterogeneous disease that affects almost everyone as patient, survivor, relative or friend. Cancer is also a major societal issue with Europe having more than 25% of the cancer cases for only 10% of the world population, a situation that will deteriorate further in our ageing societies where 13 million patients will be considered long-term cancer survivors in 2035. Developing cancer prevention, diagnosis and treatment is complex: the individuals' genetic composition, behaviour and environment all interact to determine risk and treatment outcomes. EOSC4Cancer builds on existing projects, research outcomes and established community solutions to create the federated FAIR data, analysis and services infrastructure needed for European Cancer research programmes.

Given the exponential growth in data complexity and the rapid advancements in technology, the effective analysis and interpretation of cancer research data have become critical for advancing our understanding of the disease and improving treatment outcomes. However, this pursuit is accompanied by various challenges, including the need to equip researchers with the necessary skills, facilitate seamless knowledge transfer, and foster a collaborative environment that promotes innovation and excellence.

As such, WP5 in EOSC4Cancer aims to ensure that the clinicians and cancer researchers will have the knowledge and skills on how to best address their scientific questions by using the tools and infrastructure developed in the lifecycle of the project and beyond.

This document aims to provide the preliminary structure of the “RDMkit Cancer view” content, a collaborative effort performed by different EOSC4Cancer stakeholders that aim to be the seed for creating the production-level RDMKit Cancer View web page as the final deliverable.

The document has two sections: Section 1 includes a general description of the ELIXIR Research Data Management Kit (RDMKit) and Section 2 focuses on the RDMKit Cancer view preliminary content which is aligned to the four steps in the patient journey, i.e.

1. Primary prevention (environmental and genetic factors),
2. Secondary prevention (screening),
3. Diagnoses and best treatment of localized tumors, and
4. Diagnosis and treatment of metastatic tumors,

as well as a description of the future steps to be achieved to complete and make it public as a new domain in the RDMKit web page.

2 ELIXIR Research Data Management Kit (RDMkit)

The ELIXIR Research Data Management Kit (RDMkit, <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org>) has been designed to guide life scientists in their efforts to better manage their research data following the FAIR Principles. It is based on the various steps of the data lifecycle, although not all the steps will be relevant to everyone. The RDMkit is written by and for life scientists and data stewards to help them manage their research data in a way that aligns with the FAIR Principles. The contents are mainly generated and maintained by the ELIXIR community.

- It has guidelines and best practices for managing research data throughout the data lifecycle, from planning and acquisition to analysis and dissemination.
- It has information on software tools, standards, and repositories that can be used for research data management.
- It provides contextualized links to other RDM information resources such as FAIRsharing, bio.tools, the TeSS training portal, and the FAIRCookbook.

At the heart of FAIR Science lies good data management practice. This is increasingly important as life science research becomes data-intensive and traditional 'wet labs' make space for 'dry (computer) labs'.

With that in mind, the FAIR Principles were designed to improve the **Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability** of data.

The increasing volume, complexity and speed of data creation made scientists rely on computational support exponentially. Therefore, the FAIR Principles place specific emphasis on enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use data, as well as supporting its reuse by other scientists, which facilitates knowledge discovery and improves research transparency.

More than ever, scientists need relevant tools and guidance to better manage their data and hence contribute to making FAIR Science a reality as well as help researchers be more productive for themselves and their collaborators.

- **For researchers** - RDMkit is a one-stop shop of information, advice and signposting to research data management know-how, tools, examples and best practices. Are you struggling with writing your project's data management plan? RDMkit can help.
- **For data managers in laboratories, facilities or universities** - RDMkit is a resource for your researchers, a complement to your resources and a guide to the specific challenges of RDM for life science researchers.
- **For funding agencies and policymakers** - RDMkit is the resource researchers can turn to at the proposal stage of the research, throughout their projects and when publishing their results. Remember that the cost of not having FAIR research data has been estimated at €10.2bn annually in Europe. By using RDMkit and better managing data, the outcomes of your investments will contribute to strengthening regional, national and European economies.

3 RDMKit Cancer View

The content of the RDMKit Cancer View page aims to capture the importance and challenges of management of cancer data (for clinical decision making and for cancer research). The page is structured along the patient journey (prevention, diagnosis and treatment) based on the input from the use cases WP4. Each stage of this patient journey will have a specific data management aspect that will exemplify the usage of the cancer data from the data perspective (collection, standard, reuse, etc.) and align with EOSC4Cancer use cases as the drivers of the cancer data trajectories.

The deliverable is an initial phase that includes the feedback from all contributors including EOSC4Cancer members and other stakeholders of interest. The document is currently defined by 4 different sections representing the patient journey: Primary prevention (environmental and genetic factors), Secondary prevention (screening), Diagnoses and best treatment of localized tumours, Diagnosis and treatment of metastatic tumours, as well as a section dedicated to a specific Cancer Data Type, i.e. Clinico-genomic cancer data (goal is to continue expanding this with additional types)

Future work includes:

Include content in each section by converging all contributors' text from the data perspective considering also the diversity of cancer related data (i.e human or mouse models), and align with EOSC4Cancer use cases as the drivers of the cancer data trajectories.

Follow the Research Data Life Cycle (RDLC) to identify the main sections for the RDMkit page and document best practices for each stage in the RDLC. The B1MG minimal dataset for cancer could be highlighted as a template to work with for any efforts in cancer data collection, to help with interoperability with other datasets (for data reuse).

Focus mainly on content that is strictly domain specific. If some standards or solutions apply, for instance, to genomics in general or GDPR/sensitive data in general, please reference and mention other relevant RDMkit pages or existing resources. This will help reduce duplicate efforts and ensure consistent messaging.

Try to add context as much as possible when listing resources (names, standards, links, etc.). For example the standards should not be simply listed by name in RDMkit, but context and the reasons to apply one standard or another should be clearly explained in the text. If possible, make the link between standards and public data repositories requiring or accepting specific standards (check FAIRsharing for more info).

To contact RDMkit editors for input on the structure of the sections and paragraphs within the provided template. Consult other domain pages, such as Microbial Biotechnology, as a reference for complex page structures. The ELIXIR Hub and the ELIXIR Health Data Focus Group recently published the Health data page, which shows the importance of the 'considerations' and 'solutions' sections, as well as the impact of useful descriptions of the standards recommended (see 'Electronic Health records' section).